

**RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF
STUDENT'S CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN EDUCATION AND COGNITIVE
ACTIVITY**

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Abstract: The retrospective analysis of the development of the student's creative activity in education and cognitive activity is considered in the article. The student is directed to think independently, to find his own approach to problem solving, to strive for independent acquisition of knowledge, to form a critical approach to the judgment of other people, and to achieve the independence of his judgments.

Keywords: The retrospective analysis of the development of the student's creative activity in education and cognitive activity is considered in the article. The student is directed to think independently, to find his own approach to problem solving, to strive for independent acquisition of knowledge, to form a critical approach to the judgment of other people, and to achieve the independence of his judgments.

The next ten years of higher education will be characterized by an increasing emphasis on the development of students' creative abilities and creative activity during their studies. Despite the fact that creativity belongs to the psychological-pedagogical and philosophical category, in response to the changes taking place in society today, the intensity of its research has increased significantly. In accordance with the social order of the society, the formation of the creative activity of the student, the instructions of the educational system have also changed significantly. The time of radical changes requires the formation of students who think freely and creatively, are independent, can make correct decisions, acquire knowledge independently, evaluate new information, make conscious choices, and are socially active.

No matter what changes occur in the higher education system, its pressing problem is to prepare the personnel required in the society, as well as to ensure the education, spiritual maturity and intellectual development needs of young people. Students who are always able to approach creatively in any situation are rewarded, and the task of forming such a creative and active student has been and remains relevant.

When considering any pedagogical phenomenon in order to understand its important forces, it is necessary to present it in dialectical development. To understand today's research topic, it is necessary to consider its retrospective analysis from the perspective of the past.

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In the course of research, the following concepts were hierarchically analyzed and presented: "development of creative activity", "creativity", "creative activity", "cognitive activity", "creative abilities", their interrelationship in terms of semantic development was determined and analyzed.

Many psychological and pedagogical researches are dedicated to revealing the essence of cognitive activity and its laws. An important aspect of training is the active cognitive activity of students, the need for knowledge, and the desire to acquire it. As a part of the retrospective analysis of the rise to understanding, the work presents the chronological sequence of the student in the interpretation and improvement of the basic categories of the research. Even the German democratic pedagogue A. Dichterweg emphasized that development and education cannot be given or delivered to anyone. Whoever wants to join them, must achieve it with his own strength, his own activity, his own work. The famous Russian psychologist and teacher L.V. Zankov expressed the same idea in a slightly different way and stated that real spiritual wealth is formed when the person is attracted to knowledge. The contradiction between knowledge and ignorance is important for the manifestation of need, interest, knowledge and knowledge activity.

Special attention is paid to the development of students' thinking in the framework of learning, mastering, implementation of the principles, forms of solving educational problems, and the development of the student's thinking.

One of the ways to increase student activity in education is cognitive activity. This means the ability to think independently, to act in a new situation, to find a new approach to solving problems, to acquire knowledge, to have a critical approach to the judgment of others, and the independence of one's own judgments.

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